

COST AND RETURNS OF GREEN GRAM IN BULDHANA DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The study was conducting in the Buldhana district of Maharashtra state for the year 2024-25. The three tehsils was selected from Buldhana District. Two villages from each tehsils and 20 farmers from each village was selected for present study. As such total 120 farmers was selected. A Multistage random sampling technique was adopt for the selection of sample. A schedule was designed for data collection by keeping in view the objective of study. It is concluded that the area, production and productivity of Green Gram crop in Buldhana district were unstable during period of study The per hectare yield obtained by farmers was 11.72 quintals with gross return of Rs. 76778.06 and per quintal cost of production was Rs. 5263.37. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that Green Gram registered a good input output ratio 1.23 means growing of the Green Gram is profitable venture.

Keyword: cost of cultivation, Green gram, instability, compound growth rate

Introduction

India stands as the world's largest producer and consumer of green gram, generating approximately 1.5 to 2 million tons annually from an area spanning about 3 to 4 million hectares per year. The output of green gram constitutes roughly 10 per cent of the nation's total pulse production (Ministry of Agriculture, GOI, 2024). Over the past decade, the annual growth rate of green gram production has been recorded at less than 5 percent, which is lower than the consumption growth rate of 7.60 percent. In the last five years, there has been a noticeable upward trend in both production and consumption of green gram. Nevertheless, production has not kept pace with consumption demands, necessitating imports from other countries to fulfill these requirements (Ministry of Agriculture, GOI, 2024). Green gram is recognized as a significant short-season grain legume within the traditional farming systems of both tropical and temperate regions, owing to its drought tolerance and adaptability to various soil and climatic condition. The Green gram cultivation area in the Vidarbha region spans 8.24 thousand hectares, with an average yield of 364.40 kg per hectare for the year 2023-24. The primary districts engaged in Green gram production within the Vidarbha region include Buldana, Yavatmal, Washim, Amravati, and Akola

Objective

1. Growth rates and instability in area, production and productivity in green gram.
2. To measure the cost and returns of green gram.

Methodology

The study was conducting in the Buldhana district of Maharashtra state for the year 2024-25. The three tehsils was selected from Buldhana District. Two villages from each tehsils and 20 farmers from each village was selected for present study. As such total 120 farmers was selected. A Multistage random sampling technique was adopt for the selection of sample. A schedule was designed for data collection by keeping in view the objective of study. The economics of green gram production was calculated by using standard cost concept.

Growth Rates

The compound growth rates of area, production, and productivity of green gram was estimated for last 20 year. The district wise compound

Table: 1. Compound growth rate of area, production and productivity of Green Gram in Vidarbha region.

S.N.	Particulars	Period I (2002-03 to 2011-12)	Period II (2012-13 to 2021-22)	Overall (2002-03 to 2021-22)
1	Area	-7.185*** (0.006)	-9.887 (0.012)	-8.976*** (0.003)
2	Production	-4.485 (0.031)	-8.448*** (0.025)	-8.392*** (0.009)
3	Productivity	5.166 (0.006)	2.182 (0.016)	0.226 (0.017)

(*** denotes significance at 1% level of significance)

growth rates of area, production, productivity was estimated by using following exponential model.

$$Y = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Area/Production/Productivity

a = Intercept

b = Regression Coefficient

t = Time Variable

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } Y = \text{Log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Then the percent compound growth rates(g) was computed using the relationship.

$$\text{CGR (r)} = [\text{Antilog}(\text{Log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Coefficient of Variation (CV)

Estimation of instability in area, production, and productivity of green gram was calculated by using coefficient of variation.

$$\text{CV}(\%) = \frac{\delta}{\bar{X}} \times 100$$

Where,

δ =Standard deviation

X =Arithmetic mean

Standard deviation

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=0}^n (X - \bar{X})^2}{n}}$$

S= Standard deviation

\bar{X} = Arithmetic mean

n= Number of observations

Result and Discussion

Growth rates and instability in area, production and productivity of Green Gram.

The growth performance of Green Gram pertaining to two periods and overall is discussed for Vidarbha region as under.

The information regarding compound growth rate is presented in Table 1, it was shown that at overall basis area of Green Gram was significant at 1 per cent level and production was negatively significant at 1 per cent level of significance indicates that production decreased by 8.39 per cent per annum and area decreased by 8.97 per cent per annum.

Instability in area, production and productivity of Green Gram

The agriculture performances of a particular region or state during a

Table: 2. Coefficient of variation in area, production and productivity of Green Gram in Vidarbha region.

S.N.	Particulars	Period I (2002-03 to 2011-12)	Period II (2012-13 to 2021-22)	Overall (2002-03 to 2021-22)
1	Area	26.10	49.10	54.00
2	Production	47.70	60.60	69.30
3	Productivity	33.30	40.10	35.90

given time period is measured not only from the point of view of increased in area, production and productivity but also on the extent of fluctuations taking place in the area, production and productivity rate of any crop. Here, in order to examine the extent of instability, coefficient of variation is worked out. The higher the coefficient of variation the greater is the instability and vice versa. The result obtained are presented and discussed in the table 2.

In case of area the coefficient of variation of Green Gram was 54.00 per cent. During period II highest variation was observed i.e. 49.10 per cent. In case of production at overall level the coefficient of variation of Green Gram was 69.30 per cent. during period II highest variation was observed i.e. 60.60 per cent. In case of productivity at overall level the coefficient of variation of Green Gram was 35.90 per cent. During period II highest variation was observed i.e. 40.10 per cent. It is concluded from the above discussion that the area, production and productivity of Green Gram crop in Buldhana district were unstable during period of study.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Green Gram grown by farmers is presented in Table 3

It is revealed that from the Table 3 that the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A1', cost 'A2', cost 'B1', cost 'B2', cost 'C1', cost 'C2', cost 'C3' were Rs.32726.68, Rs.32726.68, Rs. 40739.42 Rs. 53524.93, Rs. 43801.49, Rs. 56587.00 and Rs. 62245.69 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards , cost 'A1' (52.58 per cent), cost A₁ share of bullock labour 11.61 per cent, hired labour was 11.23 per cent, machine charges 4.31 per cent fertilizer 4.27 per cent, seed 4.05 per cent, plant protection 3.11 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by farmers was 11.72 quintals with gross return of Rs. 76778.06 and per quintal cost of production was Rs.5263.37

Table 3 Cost of cultivation of Green Gram

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	ITEM	Unit	Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of Input	Total Cost Per Ha.	% to Cost "C3"	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	8.01	319.32	2557.77	4.11
		Female	Days	19.06	232.48	4431.00	7.12
		Total		27.07		6988.77	11.23
2	Bullock Labour		(Pair days)	9.41	767.67	7223.77	11.61
3	Machine charges		Hours	2.68	1000.02	2680.05	4.31
4	Seed		Kg.	25.41	99.14	2519.23	4.05
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	33.56	28.46	955.37	1.53
		P	Kg.	36.52	32.37	1182.29	1.90
		K	Kg.	14.55	35.57	517.64	0.83
		Total		84.63		2655.30	4.27
7	Irrigation charges			0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Incidental charges	Rs.			1287.15	2.07	
11	Repairing Charges	Rs.			963.80	1.55	
14	Plant Protection	Rs.			1933.63	3.11	
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	Rs.			26251.70	42.17	
16	Interest on working Capital				393.78	0.63	
17	Depreciation	Rs.			6016.20	9.67	
18	Land Revenue	Rs.			65.00	0.10	
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)			0.00	32726.68	52.58	
20	Rental Value of leased Land			0.00	0.00	0.00	
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)			0.00	32726.68	52.58	
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%				8012.74	12.87	
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)				40739.42	65.45	
21	Rental Value of owned Land				12785.51	20.54	
22	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)				53524.93	85.99	
23	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	5.18	268.95	1393.15	2.24
		Female	Days	7.71	216.46	1668.92	2.68
		Total		12.89		3062.07	4.92
24	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)				43801.49	70.37	
25	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)				56587.00	90.91	
26	10% Cost C2				5658.70	9.09	

27	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)					62245.69	100.00
28	Yield per main produce hectare	Rs.		11.72	6503.33	76219.03	
29	Value of By-produce/ha.	Rs.		8.99	70.00	559.03	
30	Main Produce +By produce					76778.06	
31	Per quintal cost of Prod.					5263.37	

Per hectare cost and returns from Green Gram

The cost and returns structure per hectare of agricultural production, helps the farmer in mapping adjustment in the organization and thereby secure the optimum level of production and income. The Table 4.

Table: 4. Cost and returns from Greengram cultivation (Rs./qtl.)

S N	Particulars		Rs
1	Yield (Qtls)	Main Produce	11.72
		By Produce	8.9
2	Price/(Qtls)	Main Produce	6503.33
		By Produce	70.00
3	Value of main produce		76219.02
4	Value of by-produce		559.03
5	Value of total produce		76778.05
6	Cost of cultivation at		
a)	Cost 'A ₁ '		32726.68
b)	Cost 'A ₂ '		32726.68
c)	Cost 'B ₁ '		40739.42
d)	Cost 'B ₂ '		53524.93
e)	Cost 'C ₁ '		43801.49
f)	Cost 'C ₂ '		56587.00
g)	Cost 'C ₃ '		62245.69
7	Net return over		
a)	Cost 'A ₁ '		44051.38
b)	Cost 'A ₂ '		44051.38
c)	Cost 'B ₁ '		36038.64
d)	Cost 'B ₂ '		23253.12
e)	Cost 'C ₁ '		32976.57
f)	Cost 'C ₂ '		20191.05
g)	Cost 'C ₃ '		14532.36
8	Output input ratio at		
a)	Cost 'A ₁ '		2.35
b)	Cost 'A ₂ '		2.35
c)	Cost 'B ₁ '		1.88
d)	Cost 'B ₂ '		1.43
e)	Cost 'C ₁ '		1.75
f)	Cost 'C ₂ '		1.36
g)	Cost 'C ₃ '		1.23

indicates that at overall average gross return workout to Rs.76778.05 . This means Green Gram crop appeared to be good from monetary benefits. The input output ratio at cost C₃ was 1:1.23

Conclusion:

The compound growth rate was shown that at overall basis area of Green Gram was significant at 1 per cent level and production was negatively significant at 1 per cent level of significance indicates that production decreased by 8.39 per cent per annum and area decreased by 8.97 per cent per annum. It is concluded that the area, production and productivity of Green Gram crop in Buldhana district were unstable during period of study. The per hectare yield obtained by farmers was 11.72 quintals with gross return of Rs. 76778.06 and per quintal cost of production was Rs.5263.37. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that Green Gram registered a good input output ratio 1.23 means growing of the Green Gram is profitable venture.

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